

Exploitation of Manju Kapur's *A Married Woman*

Dr. M. Anbazhagan, M.A., M.Phil., Ph.D

*Assistant Professor of English
M.S.S.Wakf Board College, Madurai*

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Abstract

In the history of Indian English novel, women have been perceptually attempting to express their ideas, emotions and feelings through their writings. Indian women novelists exhibit their own experience and the multi-faceted experience of Indian women in their short stories and novels. The novelist, in her novels takes into account the complexity of life, different histories, cultures and different structures of values, the woman's question, despite basic solidarity, needs to be tackled in relation to the socio-cultural situation. Women under the patriarchal pressure and control are subjected to too much more brunts and social ostracism. They are more discriminated and are biased in lieu of their sex. The lives women live and struggle under the oppressive mechanism of a closed society are reflected in the writings of Manju Kapur. One can see the budding of new women in Manju Kapur's heroines, who do not want to be mere puppets for others to move as they like. Defying patriarchal notions that enforce women towards domesticity, they assert their individuality and aspire self-reliance through education. They nurture the desire of being independent and leading lives of their own. They are not silent rebels but are bold, outspoken, determined and action-oriented.

Keywords: patriarchal pressure, discrimination, oppression, bias.

Kapur seems to be aware of the fact that the women of India have indeed achieved their success in sixty years of independence, but if there is to be a true female independence too much remains to be done. The conflict for autonomy and separate identity remains an unfinished battle. Women under the patriarchal pressure and control were subjected to much more brunts and social ostracism. They were discriminated and were biased in lieu of their sex. The lives of Indian women and their struggle under the oppressive mechanism of a closed patriarchal society were reflected in the novels of Manju Kapur. She deals with the position of woman as a daughter, a wife and a mother. "All her female protagonists railing from middle class status challenge the existing socio-cultural patriarchal system. In the social milieu they are educated, modern, intelligent bold and assertive" (Pradhan 116). Even though they try to transcend the social hierarchy by demolishing it, they often undergo serious psychological traumas in the absence of an alternative, planned feminist ideology that may give them freedom, security and peace of mind.

Feminism emerges as a concept that is based on a critical analysis of male privilege and woman's subordination within any given

society. It opposes woman's subordination to men in the family and society. Feminism is a global and revolutionary ideology that is political because it is concerned with the question of power. In the words of P.C. Pradhan: "Feminism as a philosophy, challenges the patriarchal symbolic order, social organization and control mechanism. It, therefore, opposes women's subordination and oppression in home and society" (108). A feminist is one who is awakened and conscious about woman's life and problems. Themes explored in feminism and feminist theory include patriarchy, sexual objectification and oppression. Feminists argue that inequality between the sexes is not the result of biological necessity but is produced by the cultural construction of gender differences. Sex refers to the determining of identity on the basis of biological category while gender connotes the cultural meaning attached to sexual identity. In other words gender is the product of cultural conditioning.

Manju Kapur, a powerful exponent of feminism has denounced the Indian women's socio-cultural predicament caused by their entrapment in male-dominant socio-economic culture and political hegemony of patriarchal society. She has expressed such feminist views in her second novel *A Married Woman* (2002) in the context of post-modernism. Manju Kapur has successfully enabled her woman protagonist Astha in *A Married Woman* to construct a femino-centric protest and help her wriggle out from the stifling patriarchal institutions like family and married life. She becomes fully aware of the enormous burden of gender discrimination in her respective culture and society. She understands that all over the world all history is male-centered. He has used her to promote his physical and material comforts. "At the same time he has never taken any meaningful steps to elevate her to that rank she was created to fill, namely an equal partner to her male companion. Conversely, he has done everything to debase and enslave her mind and body" (Gnanamony, *Literary Dialectics* 161). So the space of a woman in the human world is biologically limited. Her existence in the male world is unlimitedly controlled by so many factors--sociological, biological, cultural, religious and moral.

Astha, the female protagonist of Manju Kapur's *A Married Woman* gives a stiff resistance to patriarchy by helping her "metamorphosed into a feminist odd ball" (162). Astha, the daughter of an educated father and an orthodox mother, she is discriminated against and subjugated at her in-law's house. Her marriage with Hemant, the son of a government official in Delhi, does not prove to be based on mutual co-operation and understanding. She is compelled to be an enduring wife and sacrificing mother, like a holy cow in the status of married woman. There, she is supposed to have a willing body at night, a willing pair of hands and feet in the day and an obedient mouth. It leads to her physical exploitation and emotional starvation. Being deprived of her emotional fulfilment, she frantically searches for it and turns to lesbianism. Manju Kapur in her novel *A Married Woman* through the protagonist Astha, "has carved out an independent life of the woman for self-fulfillment and advocated for inter-religious marriage and female-female bond contrary to be patriarchal norms of traditional society" (Prasad Singh 71). *A Married Woman* reveals a woman's obsession with love and lesbianism.

The protagonist of the novel Astha is a typical middle-class woman brought up in Delhi. She succumbs to her parents finding her husband in a traditionally arranged manner. "Within the bounds of marriage, she discovers a latent sexuality that is driven by love and passion and her desire is to assert her individualism" (qtd. in Prasad and Joseph 196). As Astha was the only child to her parents, her education, her character, her health, her marriage, were the burdens of her parents. In fact, she was their future, their hope and though she did not want them to guard her so carefully, they did. But Astha's mother, being a traditional family woman, prayed for Astha's future thus: "Everyday in her temple corner in the kitchen, she prayed for a good husband for her daughter" (*A Married Woman* 01). Astha's father also took an enormous care for his daughter. In the mean

time, Astha became sixteen. She was well trained on a diet of “mushy novels and thoughts of marriage” (08). Unlike many unmarried girls she had her infatuations of adolescent love for Bunty, a handsome soldier boy who frequented his visits to her house and for Rohan who left for overseas for a better career. Astha liked Bunty very much. But her interest in Bunty was short-lived. Astha’s mother became instrumental in sowing the seeds of discord in her daughter’s friendship with Bunty. Astha was unable to forget her Bunty. Shortly a suitor came for Astha. As she had just come from college, tired and was stinking with sweat, she was not at all ready to meet the stranger. Astha remained in the bathroom long after her suitor had left. Manju Kapur sarcastically says, “The bathroom represented her future; she had better start getting acquainted with it now”(22).

In the mean time, obviously suspecting something fishy in Astha’s secret life, her parents “tightened their surveillance” (28). Rohan, her boy friend, did very well in the exam and like his father, went to Oxford for his higher studies. She had become a victim of male passion. Rohan went abroad and Astha enrolled in M.A., “bored and unenthusiastic” (31). Astha had a proposal from a US returned MBA chap. She was wondering whether she should tell him “though she had kissed a boy, her hymen was intact” (35). The engagement was over and both started dating. The marriage took place on an auspicious day. Rohan, her boyfriend, had abandoned her, Hemant had married her, he valued her, and he thought her so charming. In their honeymoon in Kashmir, he told her that he was happy because he wanted to marry “an innocent, unspoilt, simple girl” (41). That was fulfilled for he was so sure that Astha was a virgin. But Astha asked herself “Had she been a virgin?”(41). As such thoughts were useless, she decided to stop thinking about the past.

That Astha used to write and paint was known to her husband. Reading a poem Astha had composed, Hemant said, “May be I can help you” (*A Married Woman* 42). All Astha said was, “Really!” (42). She would have felt that this was another aspect of male chauvinism. That wives have to dance to all sorts of tunes of their husbands is not unusual in the Indian domestic space. As Astha wanted to be different, she tried to make her husband understand that she was an individual and she must get her due respect and she could never tolerate to be a doormat. In the bedroom, Hemant wanted her to wear sexy clothes. Balking she would ask him, “What do you think I am? A whore?” (44). On another occasion, Astha was looking at a black thing he offered to her. She asked him what it was. He said, “a teddy” (44). She asked him in annoyance, “So I am to be your teddy bear?” (44). Hemant felt unhappy with her reply. Within a few months, dullness began to taint Astha’s married life. She had to wait all day long for her husband’s arrival. She took up a teaching assignment in Delhi and enjoyed it very much. But back in home sometimes she had to wait very long for her husband (who was employed in a bank) to draw his attention to her.

Hemant behaves like a typical male in the orient. He did not care much to the inmost longings of his wife. He even denies Astha’s just demand of having a baby. She had to repeatedly plead to him to stop using birth control devices. Hemant loved her even after Anu was born to them. However, she didn’t like the way he pushed her into the bathroom to have sex with her. He would pacify her saying, “How do you think half the country fucks? You think they have separate rooms?” (60). She didn’t like the leer on Hemant’s face. Her longing for a better relationship with him did not materialize. In the domestic space, Hemant behaves like a typical hyper masculine. In other words, “he is a proud member of a patriarchal society dominated by machismo and heterosexuality” (Gnanamony, *Literary Polyrhythms* 105). As the earth is conquered, women must also be conquered. If a man is successful in conquering his woman, then this morale will be very high. Otherwise he will feel very shaky. As Ania Loomba observes in her classic text *Colonialism/Post Colonialism* : “[...] female bodies symbolise the conquered land” (152). Hemant’s attitude to his wife is nothing short of this.

Thus Astha initially finds love and companionship, but following the birth of her two children, she begins to find that she has sacrificed her own identity while striving to satisfy the traditional

duties and family values. Her family affairs are also not so good and nothing is right with her. As a married woman she becomes an enduring wife and sacrificing mother. "Her temperamental incompatibility with her corporate thinking husband compels her to play the role of mother and father for her children (*A Married Woman* 189). This denies her self-fulfillment and leads to the collapse of the institution of marriage. Discontentment leads her to defiance and restlessness. Astha understands a married woman's place in the family to be that of an unpaid servant or a slave and thought of divorce brings social and economic death in her Indian status. She is "always adjusting to everybody's need" (227). She has no emotional freedom from the domestic affairs. She has to please her husband and for pleasing him, she must be "A willing body at night, a willing pair of hands and feet in the day and an obedient mouth" (231). So she joins as a teacher but this job also does not set her free from distress and stress of discrimination. Astha is thus torn between her duty and responsibility, faith and fact, history and contemporaneity, public ethos and personal ethics. She struggles for an emotional freedom from the scourge of family. She develops psycho-somatic symptoms of stress and depression balancing between existing and living.

Manju Kapur attacks the Indian attitude of preferring a baby-boy to a baby-girl in the novel. When her daughter Anuradha was four, Astha conceived again. As the seniors in the family had expected, the baby was a son. He was Christened as Himanshu. Now Astha got all that she wanted. She felt satisfied for "she had partaken of the archetypal experiences marked out for the female race" (69). Having given birth to Himanshu- a son, she did not feel inferior to anyone in society and family members are grateful to her because they felt "the family is complete at last" (68).

Like a typical Indian father, Hemant wanted Astha to take of the baby-boy. As the novel says, "the last thing he wished to bother about was taking care of a child" (70). He said that it was her job and he had nothing to do with it. He said firmly, "It's woman's work hire somebody to help you, or quit your job" (70). Astha was struck dumb. In the mean time, Hemant's business prospered and he travelled to South Korea and Japan. Gradually their house started acquiring the gloss of a house with money. But such things did not make Astha happy. She was now "virtually a single matter" (71). Due to some tension or other, Astha had a terrible headache. She had to be operated on, yet the headache returned. In the mean time, she had composed some two hundred poems. These poems talked about her experiences endlessly replayed. Her poem, "Changes" very beautifully presents her pain, longing and determination:

I would never suffer again
But no matter how many times
I leave the doorways of my soul
To let the chill light in
The darkness grows silently
To hide me in the break of day. (81)

On reading it, Hemant felt that these lines sounded bleak. He also noticed that the person behind those poems was a positive neurotic. Astha protested that the poems were not about her.

It was just then Astha came into contact with Aijaz Akhtar Khan, the founder of the Street Theatre Group. Aijaz, a muslim lecturer in history, was a good artist and he appreciated Astha's drawings very much. Shortly, Astha heard that Aijaz Khan was engaged to Pipeelika Trivedi, a Hindu Brahmin girl living in Delhi. Pipee's mother was horrified when she learned that her daughter was marrying a Muslim. Having been a postgraduate in Economics, she joined an NGO run by three women, dealing with alternative education for slum children. Pipee had a lot of hair, it sprung up all around her head in waves and curls and frizzes. Aijaz loved it, "loved it almost as much as he loved her breasts, large and full of give" (123). They married in September 1988. No relatives were present from either side. A year later in 1989, Aijaz and the Street Theatre Group

travelled to Rajpur. Aijaz Khan and his troupe were burned alive in their van. Reading it in the newspapers, Astha wept openly. When she went to school that day, “numbly Astha put on a white saree” (140). Usually Indian women wear white when their husbands pass away. Four days later, Astha joined a massive procession was organized in Delhi to the Prime Minister’s residence to present a memorandum to him to put an end to communal orgies. Shortly Astha made a trip to Ayodhya to study the communal situation there. It was there she met Pipee for the first time. She was attracted to her hair instantly.

As a boy is attracted to a girl in the courtship period, Astha was drawn to Pipee. As both their hearts were empty at that time, it was rather easy for them to come closer. Astha sat in a daze after reaching home from Ayodhya. She couldn’t believe that she had met Pipee and had been with her for many hours. Next morning, when she packed her husband’s suitcase, she saw a condom. She stared at it for a long time. Its implications ran through her head. Astha takes a sweet revenge on her husband. In this act of vengeance, unnatural sex, little excitement, little impatience and much imagination, she has a big jerk in her mind and this cripples her married life. As Astha had a substitute husband in Pipee, she did not create any scene at all in the condom episode. Rather she thought that if her husband had an extra ‘other’ in his life, she could also have an extra ‘other’ a kind of Old Testament tit-for-tat attitude. Both Pipee and Astha seem to be aware of this hidden truth. They started meeting each other quite often. Both became very chummy friends. Pipee put her hand on Astha’s and pressed it gently. Astha blushed with pleasure. An element of secrecy entered their relationship and gave it an illicit character. Hemant caught a whiff of this extra, unusual interest in his wife’s life. But he was not unduly perturbed about it. From the behaviour of Astha and Pipee one can understand that as far as sexuality is concerned, it is not something biologically given, or transmitted by genes, rather it is a cultural construct which is learned in society due to certain circumstantial constraints. Once Pipee took to her bathroom mirror and asked her to have a close look at her figure. On her way back home in her scooter, Astha felt lost and confused. The image of the two of them in the mirror was often returning when she thought of Pipee. On another occasion, they met in Astha’s bedroom. Pipee pressed Astha’s fingers into her mouth and sucked each one gently before letting go. Astha hardly dared to breathe. That night when Hemant started his sex routine, Astha said for the first time in her married life that she did not like it. Astha’s meetings with Pipee increased. They phoned up atleast five times a day. Astha “started to fantasise about touching her, imagined her hair between her fingers, her skin beneath her own, her hand on the back of her neck” (225). As they drove the streets of Delhi in Astha’s car, “Astha leaned against Pipee with her arms around her waist” (227). As Jyotirmaya Tripathy observes elsewhere that their sexual conduct shows “that an alternative exists and that is not less enjoyable, that sexuality does not mean pulverization of the female principle, and lionization of a dominant male. It proves that sexuality is a pleasure, not a power structure” (290). Astha found a satisfaction that she did not get from her husband.

Astha thus chose an alternative form of sexual identity willingly “to destabilize the entire system of sex regulation, that undoes binary oppositions such as gay/straight” (qtd. in Stuart Sim 345). Astha, the married woman, knew pretty well that the heterocratic society distinguishes man from woman. In this binary opposed mindset, lesbians have no place and they will never be tolerated as they are seem increasingly defying the definition of man and the grammar of man-woman relationship. As Gnanamony in his *Literary Polyrythms* aptly observes, “Astha’s taking the stance as a lesbian is vociferously against heterosexuality, and its normativity and institutionalization. Her stance is a protest, as in the words of Jyotirmaya Tripathy, against “heterosexual master identity, its logic of domination, its demonization of other sexual practices, and its rejection of sexual diversity” (290).

As days went by, a great change came upon Astha. She was in a state of continued war with everything around her, and her self. She could never truly find peace with herself. She was fast creating a space for her as a lesbian by making Pipee her steady sweetheart. Through this process she released herself from obsession with her male partner, her husband. She was also conscious that she was a wife too. After sometime, Astha too realized that any relationship, even that between a woman and another woman, becomes demanding after a length of time. Pipee wanted Astha totally committed to her but Astha was not willing to divorce herself from her old life. Yet such a relationship could continue only between two people who are firm and strong and totally resolved to live together. Astha, however, was not a strong woman. She could never be bold enough to leave her marriage and live with Pipee. After Astha's trip with her family to Disney world and London the relationship broke down irreparably. Pipee decided to go to America to pursue her Ph.D. and Astha returned to her old life. Astha continued her paintings and found an outlet for her pent-up rage. Through Astha, Kapur offers a frontal challenge to patriarchal thought, Manju Kapur empowers her protagonist Astha to give a strong resistance to patriarchy by denouncing the prescribed norms of a society. Through such resistance she attains psychological freedom and individual needs in her life.

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